

Probability of coincidence in disease selection for consecutive years in Colombia and between Colombia and Central America, 1985-86.^a

Disease	Colombia ^b	Central America	χ^2
Leaf blast	0.83	0.88	1.54 (0.1 < P < 0.9)
Leaf scald	0.93	0.85	2.75 (0.05 < P < 0.1)
Brown spot	–	0.79	–

^aProbability of coincidence: probability for a line to be selected in those locations in Central America with moderate to severe disease levels, given that it was selected in Colombia. ^bBS pressure was too low in 1986; thus no selection was made.

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Rice cultures with early plant resistance to bacterial blight (BB)

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BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye, a serious disease of wet season (1 Jun-30 Nov) rice in eastern Uttar Pradesh, is more damaging during the early crop season when temperature and atmospheric humidity are very high. Only the prebooting stage of long-duration varieties coincides with this period.

We tested a number of cultures for prebooting stage resistance to BB during 1986-87 wet season. Each entry was sown in two 2-m-long rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Plants were clip-inoculated with a suspension of a local BB isolate at tillering and rated at 15 d and 30 d after inoculation. TN1 at maximum tillering was the susceptible check.

Eight test cultures had disease scores of 2, 15 had scores of 3 (see table). □

Rice cultures showing early (prebooting stage) plant resistance to local BB pathogen isolate. Faizabad, U. P., India, 1986.

Variety or culture	Cross	Disease ^a score
RP1860-102-23-4-3	IET5656/Salamat	2
MTU7633	VasistalMahsuri	2
CR210-1018	Pankaj/Jagannath	2
CR98-7269	L. Z. Nira/TN1	2
CR260-131-5	CR151/CR1014	2
OR142-29	Pankaj/Sigadis	2
OR142-93	Pankaj/Sigadis	2
OR151-17	Hema/CR51-1523//Vikram	2
CR149-7171-271	MNP36/CR12//Pankaj	3
CR149-206	CR63-5218-1/Pankaj	3
CR98-8081	L. Z. Nira/TN1	3
MTU5182	MTU4569/ARC6650	3
CN836-3-6	–	3
CN836-3-8	–	3
CR376-KR-1	–	3
CR376-KR-2	–	3
CR376-KR-3	–	3
RAU83-8-4	BR-51-46-51/Mahsuri	3
RP1859-206-6-4-2-1	Swarnadhan/Benong III	3
RP1860-249-3-1-1	Swarnadhan/Salamat	3
RP1641-11-5-1-B	Vikram/Bulu Benong III	3
RP1641-44-7	–	3
RP1641-144-11-B	–	3
TN1 (check)	–	3

^aBased on *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1980).

Insect resistance

Gall midge (GM) resistance in traditional rice varieties in Bihar

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Seven local rice varieties collected from endemic GM areas of Chhotanagpur plateau, Bihar, were evaluated for resistance in 1984-86 wet seasons. Two resistant and one susceptible high-yielding varieties were included for

comparison. One-month-old seedlings were planted in 3- × 4-m plots with 3 replications. Silvershoot percentage was recorded at peak infestation (45 d after transplanting).

Local variety Baghpanjar consistently showed resistant reactions comparable to those of resistant checks RD202 and Shakti (Table 1). When 3-yr data were pooled, all varieties except Dhusri were better than Jaya. Baghpanjar matched the resistant checks. However, susceptible Jaya recorded the highest yield (Table 2). □

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Table 1. Silvershoots in GM resistance trials. Bihar, India, 1984-86.

Variety	Silvershoots ^a (%)			
	1984	1985	1986	Mean ^b
Kalamdani	2.13 (4.54)	1.00 (1.00)	3.23 (10.43)	2.13 (4.54) c
Baghpanjar	1.83 (3.35)	1.60 (2.56)	0.60 (0.36)	1.34 (1.80) ab
Bhojni	2.73 (7.45)	1.20 (1.44)	2.63 (6.92)	2.20 (4.08) c
Saraikele	0.87 (0.76)	1.77 (3.13)	2.63 (6.92)	1.76 (3.10) bc
Dhusri	3.13 (9.80)	1.73 (3.00)	3.63 (13.18)	2.83 (8.00) d
Karnusal	2.97 (8.82)	2.13 (4.54)	4.50 (20.25)	3.30 (9.18) de
Bheri-rice	3.03 (9.18)	1.37 (1.88)	3.13 (9.80)	2.51 (6.30) cd
Jaya (susceptible check)	4.37 (19.10)	3.20 (10.24)	4.63 (21.44)	4.07 (16.60) e
RD202 (resistant check)	1.10 (1.21)	1.40 (1.96)	0.60 (0.36)	1.03 (1.06) a
Shakti (resistant check)	2.10 (4.41)	0.63 (0.40)	1.50 (2.25)	1.41 (2.00) ab
CD (0.05)	0.89	1.15	0.86	0.93

^aFigures in parentheses = original values. ^bValues followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 2. Yield in GM resistance trial. Bihar, India, 1984-86.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)			
	1984	1985	1986	Mean ^a
Kalamdani	4.3	1.2	2.1	2.5
Baghpanjar	2.4	1.5	3.3	2.4
Bhojni	3.7	0.7	2.8	2.4
Saraikele	2.6	1.5	2.8	2.3
Dhusri	3.7	1.4	2.9	2.7
Karnusal	3.3	0.6	2.8	2.2
Bheri-rice	3.0	0.8	2.4	2.1
Jaya	4.0	1.2	2.9	2.7
RD202	3.6	1.2	2.5	2.5
Shakti	2.6	0.8	3.8	2.4

Adverse soils tolerance

Growth recovery from salt stress during initial seedling stage

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In the southern and eastern part of India near the sea, the rice crop is affected by tides at the early seedling stage. We studied the effect of salinity on seedling growth after removal of salt stress.

The experiment was conducted in petri dishes at electrical conductivity (EC) of 1.5 and 13.6 dS/m. Forty seeds each of Jaya (tolerant) and Basmati 370 (sensitive) varieties were placed in petri dishes lined with filter paper Whatman No. 1, with 30 replications. Seeds were surface-sterilized by 0.1% mercuric chloride solution.

Salinity stress was removed 4, 6, and 8 d after sowing (DAS) by washing 10 replications/treatment with water at EC 1.5 dS/m. Two replications were removed at each sampling to measure length of root, shoot, dry weight of root and shoot, endosperm part, and recovery rate.

Salinity retarded root and shoot

Carryover effect of salinity at seedling stage on root and shoot length after stress removal, Ludhiana, India. Arrows indicate days when stress was removed.

growth. On removal of salt stress, seedlings began to recover.

Initial recovery in root and shoot length was better when stress was